

Effect of Low-Loading Nanoparticles on the Tribological Property of Short Carbon Fiber (SCF)/PTFE/Graphite Reinforced PEEK

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SUMMARY

The effects of low-loading nano-SiO₂ particles (13 nm, 1 vol.%) on the dynamic mechanical properties and the tribological characteristics, i.e. friction coefficient and wear rate, of SCF/PTFE/graphite filled PEEK were studied in the present work. The tribological mechanisms of the nanocomposite were discussed.

Keywords: Tribology; nanocomposite; PEEK; Short-carbon-fiber composite

INTRODUCTION

Polymer composites are being much used as tribomaterials due to their light weights and good tribological performances [1-4]. Polymeric material filled with SCF and micro-sized internal lubricants, e.g. PTFE and graphite, is a successful tribomaterial formulation [5]. Poly-ether-ether-ketone (PEEK) is an outstanding thermoplastic with excellent mechanical properties, e.g. high stiffness, toughness and cohesive strength. In addition, it has a high glass transition and melting temperatures [6,7]. As excellent candidates for many tribological applications, SCF filled PEEK composites are widely used where friction reduction and wear resistance are important issues [5,8-10]. Under a low apparent pressure, the fiber thinning dominates the wear behavior of the fibre-reinforced PEEK composites. Under a high pressure and especially at a high velocity, however, the breakdown, debonding and removal of SCF result in a much increased wear rate [5,11].

Nanoparticles reinforced polymers attract more and more attentions due to their unique properties resulting from the nanoscale structures. The extremely high specific surface area is one of the most attractive characteristics of nanoparticles because it facilitates creating a great amount of interphase in a composite and thereby, a strong interaction between the fillers and the matrix even at a rather low nano-filler loading [12]. The incorporation of nanoparticles into polymer matrix often leads to a decrease in the wear rate of polymer [1,4,11-20]. Considering the importance of nano-filler/matrix interaction, the nanoparticle/matrix adhesion and the dispersion state of the nano-fillers can play a key role

in the tribological performances of the nanocomposites. A homogeneous dispersion of the nanoparticles and a good nanoparticle/matrix bonding are shown to contribute better to the property improvement [4,16]. In our previous work [14], the tensile and tribological properties of nano-SiO₂ (13 nm) filled PEEK compounded using a ball-milling technique were studied. The incorporation of nano-SiO₂ leads to a significant improvement in matrix stiffness. Nanoparticle-induced molecular or morphological immobilization can be responsible for the enhanced stiffness. After incorporating nano-SiO₂, the wear rate of PEEK is significantly decreased and at a very low nano-SiO₂ content, i.e. 1 vol%, the composite presents the optimum wear resistance. In recent years, nanocalc [21] or sub-micro inorganic particles [22, 23] were incorporated into SCF filled polymers to improve the tribological performances of the micro-sized fillers reinforced composites. Guo [21] et al. and Zhang et al. [22] found that the incorporation of nanoparticles or sub-micro particles into SCF reinforced epoxy leads to the best tribological performance. That is, the hybrid composites show better wear resistance than the composites filled uniquely with the conventional fillers or with nano (or sub-micro) fillers. The incorporation of sub-micro ZnS (300 nm) and TiO₂ (300 nm) particles into SCF/graphite filled PEEK does not show positive effects on the wear resistance of the composite at room temperature [23]. Nevertheless, under temperatures higher than 70 °C, the fine particles significantly decrease the wear rate of the PEEK composite [23]. In order to improve the room temperature property of the conventional composite, a reduction of the particle size to nanoscale can be solution.

The objectives of this work are to investigate the roles of nanoscale particles on the tribological performance of SCF filled PEEK and to deepen the comprehension on the mechanisms by which nanoparticles modify the tribological performances of SCF filled polymer composites.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials

Commercially available SCF/PTFE/graphite (micro-sized, 10 wt.% for each) filled PEEK granules supplied by Evonik (Germany) were used. Fumed silica (Aerosil[®] 7200) with a methacrylsilane surface treatment was used as nano-fillers. The nanoparticles have an average size of 13 nm and a specific area of 125-175 m²/g. The compounding of nano-SiO₂ with the composite granules was carried out using a laboratory-scale melting mixer (Brabender[®] kneader) at 410 °C and a rotation speed of 60 min⁻¹ for 10 min. The content of nano-SiO₂ was 1 vol.% (1.51 wt.%). The traditional fillers reinforced composite (without nano-SiO₂) and the nanocomposite were compression molded at 410 °C into plates and slowly cooled to room temperature. For simplification, the two composites are designated according to their components as PEEK/SCF/PTFE/graphite and PEEK/SCF/PTFE/graphite/nano-SiO₂, respectively. The specimens for tribological tests were cut from the compression molded plates with a dimension of 4 × 4 × 12 mm³.

DMTA

The storage modulus and damping $\tan\delta$ of the conventional and the nanocomposite were examined by Dynamic Mechanical Thermal Analysis (DMTA) on a Gabo Qualimeter Eplexor 150 N in a tensile testing configuration. The temperature range varied from $-100\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ to $250\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, at a heating rate of $2\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$. The amplitude of the static load was chosen to be 40 N that of the dynamic load 20 N , at a constant frequency of 10 Hz .

Tribological Test

Tribological tests were performed using a block-on-ring apparatus at room temperature ($21\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$). The counterpart was a 100Cr6 steel ring with a 60 mm diameter and a mean roughness, R_a , $0.2\text{ }\mu\text{m}$. In order to reduce the running-in process, before the tests the specimens were “pre-worn” with grinding papers (firstly P600 and then P1200) to an arc outline matching the counterpart configuration. The apparent pressure varied from 1 MPa to 7 MPa and the sliding velocity varied from 1 m/s to 2 m/s . All the tests in this work were conducted for 20 hours under dry sliding conditions. The friction forces were measured dynamically during the tests and the specific wear rates of the composites were calculated after the tests. The worn surfaces were inspected by a Scanning Electronic Microscopy (SEM, JEOL JSM-6300) after sputtering a thin gold layer.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

DMTA

Fig. 1 shows the storage modulus and damping $\tan\delta$ of the conventional and the nanocomposite. It is clear that nano- SiO_2 particles significantly increase the storage modulus of the composite. Especially near the glass transition temperature (T_g) of PEEK, the nanoparticles decrease the damping $\tan\delta$.

Fig. 1. DMTA results of the composites with and without the nanoparticles.

Friction Coefficient and Wear Rate

Fig. 2a shows the effect of apparent pressure on the mean friction coefficients of the composites with and without nano-SiO₂. The sliding velocity is 1 m/s. It is clear that within the studied range the addition of nano-SiO₂ significantly decreases the friction coefficients. Fig. 2b shows the effect of sliding velocity on the friction coefficient under 5 MPa. In the whole studied range, i.e. from 1 m/s to 2 m/s, the nanoparticles remarkably reduce the friction coefficients.

Fig. 2. Effects of apparent pressure (a) and sliding velocity (b) on the mean friction coefficients of PEEK/SCF/PTFE/graphite and PEEK/SCF/PTFE/graphite/nano-SiO₂. The sliding velocity and apparent pressure in a and b are respectively 1 m/s and 5 MPa.

Fig. 3a shows the effect of apparent pressures on specific wear rates of the two composites. The sliding velocity is 1 m/s. As shown in the figures, under 1 MPa nanoparticles play a negative effect on the wear resistance of the traditional fillers reinforced composite. Nevertheless, under pressures higher than 2 MPa, the nanocomposite presents remarkably lower wear rates than the composite only with traditional fillers. Fig. 3b illustrates the effect of sliding velocity on the specific wear rates measured under 5 MPa. The increase in sliding velocity from 1 m/s to 2 m/s, give a rise to the specific wear rate of the composite without nano-SiO₂. With respect to the nanoparticles filled composite, however, the increase in sliding velocity decreases the specific wear rate. The positive effect of nano-SiO₂ on the wear resistance is more pronounced at high velocities.

Fig. 3. Effects of apparent pressure (a) and sliding velocity on the specific wear rates of PEEK/SCF/PTFE/graphite and PEEK/SCF/PTFE/graphite/nano-SiO₂. The sliding velocity and apparent pressure in a and b are respectively 1 m/s and 5 MPa.

Discussions on Tribological Mechanisms

Fig. 4a shows the worn surface of PEEK/SCF/PTFE/graphite produced under [1 MPa, 1 m/s]. The sliding direction is indicated by a thick arrow. As can be clearly seen, the SCF surface is smooth and no obvious failure of SCF is noticed. It is clear that the thinning of fibers mainly determines the tribological behavior under this condition. Fig. 4b shows the worn surface of PEEK/SCF/PTFE/graphite/nano-SiO₂ produced under the same condition. The worn surface presents distinctly different morphology from that of the composite reinforced only with traditional fillers. The SCF/PEEK interface becomes unclear and some of fibers are destroyed. Fig. 4c shows a fiber the worn surface with a high magnification. The fiber outline is sketched on the image by a dashed oval. The surface of the fiber is very rough and some cracks occur in the fiber as indicated by white arrows. The failures of fibers are assumed to originate from possible nano-SiO₂ agglomerates. The abrasiveness exerted by nano-SiO₂ agglomerates severing as a “third-body” seems to severely destroy the fibers. This can be the reason why the incorporation of nano-SiO₂ decreases the wear resistance of the composite under a low pressure.

Fig. 5a shows the worn surface of PEEK/SCF/PTFE/graphite produced under [5 MPa, 1 m/s]. Deep scratch traces generated by the scratch by broken fibers are noticed in some zones on the worn surface. As aforementioned, under a high pressure, the failures of fibers dominate the tribological performance of the conventional composite. Fig. 5b shows that in some zones SCF separates from the matrix. The separation of SCF/PEEK is assumed to be a result of the interfacial fatigue occurring in some zones where fibers are most highly loaded. Under high pressures, the fibers bear high tension and shear stresses [24, 25]. In addition, due to the distinctly different modulus of SCF and the matrix, stress transferring occurs on SCF/PEEK interface in the surface layer involved into friction. The stress concentration occurring on SCF can lead to a significant deformation of SCF along the sliding direction. Due to repeated effects, the high stress and strain of SCF can cause

failures of SCF/PEEK interfaces in the zones where fibers are highly loaded. It should be noted that further efforts are required to verify the interface fatigue.

Fig. 4. Worn surfaces produced under [1 MPa, 1m/s] of PEEK/SCF/PTFE/graphite (a) and PEEK/SCF/PTFE/graphite/nano-SiO₂ with low (b) and high (c) magnifications.

Fig. 5. Worn surface of PEEK/SCF/PTFE/graphite produced under [5 MPa, 1 m/s] with low (a) and high (b) magnifications.

Fig. 6a shows the worn surface of PEEK/SCF/PTFE/graphite/nano-SiO₂ produced under [5 MPa, 1 m/s]. Fig. 6b shows the typical SCF/PEEK interface with a high magnification. With comparing the worn surfaces of the two composites, two features can be addressed. Firstly, incorporated nano-SiO₂ significantly protects the SCF/PEEK bonding during the sliding process and therefore no obvious SCF/PEEK interfacial failure is noticed. This can be the main reason why the wear resistance is improved after incorporating nano-SiO₂. Secondly, slight plough marks are observed on fiber surfaces. These plough marks are attributed to the sliding of crushed nanoparticle agglomerates. Under a high pressure, the big agglomerates of the nanoparticles can be crushed under an elevated compressive stress. This is the reason why the agglomerates do not result in so severe SCF destructions as in the case under a low pressure. From the above results and discussions, it can be concluded that for the studied system the pressure 2 MPa is a critical value. Under a pressure higher than the critical value, large nanoparticle agglomerates will be crushed into small ones which will no longer exert severe abrasions on SCF. However, it should be noted that a different velocity or a different dispersion state of the nanoparticles can change the critical pressure. As indicated before, the increase in sliding velocity from 1 m/s to 2 m/s gives rise to the specific wear rate of PEEK/SCF/PTFE/graphite. For the nanocomposite, however, the increase in sliding velocity from 1 m/s to 2 m/s slightly decreases the wear. At a higher velocity, the nanoparticle agglomerates can be crushed into smaller ones than these produced at a lower velocity due to the higher dynamics of the counterpart. Moreover, with increasing the sliding velocity, the crushed agglomerates tend to change their movement patterns from sliding to rolling [27].

Fig. 6. Worn surface of PEEK/SCF/PTFE/graphite/nano-SiO₂ produced under [5 MPa, 1 m/s] with low (a) and high (b) magnifications.

After incorporating nanoparticles into PEEK matrix, two factors can simultaneously protect the SCF/matrix interface. As schematized in Fig. 7, in zone I (in front of SCF), the increased stiffness of PEEK by incorporating the nanoparticles can reduce the stress concentration on SCF. During the sliding process, stress transferring from matrix to the nanoparticles occurs in the frictional layer and therefore the stress concentration on fibers can be reduced. Additionally, in zone II (behind SCF), the increased stiffness of PEEK can

reduce the deformation of SCF under a tension stress. These two factors are supposed to reduce SCF failures in the sliding process. Moreover, the contact temperature can also influence the tribological performance of the two composites. As well know, most of frictional force is transformed to heat and thus gives rise to contact temperature. Due to the fact that the friction coefficients of the nanocomposite are lower than these of the conventional composite, it is reasonably assumed that the interfacial temperature of the former is also lower than the conventional composite. This can be another factor contributing to the improvement of the wear resistance.

Fig. 7. Schematic illustration of the effect of the nanoparticles on SCF/matrix interface.

CONCLUSIONS

The effects of low-loading (1 vol.%) nano-SiO₂ particles (13 nm) on the dynamic mechanical property and the tribological performance of SCF/PTFE/graphite filled PEEK were studied in this work. Tribological tests were performed under extremely variant conditions, i.e. apparent pressure varying from 1 MPa to 7 MPa and sliding velocity varying from 1 m/s to 2 m/s. The incorporated nanoparticles significantly increase the storage modulus of the composite and decrease its damping $\tan \delta$ near glass transition temperater (T_g)

The nanoparticles remarkably reduces the friction coefficients of the composite. The roles of nano-SiO₂ on the wear rate show a strong dependence on the apparent pressure. Under 1 MPa, the nanoparticles play a negative role: the incorporation of nano-SiO₂ largely increases the wear rate of the composite. While under pressures higher than 2 MPa, the nanoparticles reduce the wear rate of the composite. The positive effect of the nanoparticles is more pronounced under high pressures and especially at high velocities. Obviously, the nanoparticles increase the pv limit of the composite. Under a low pressure, when possible nanoparticle agglomerates lead to severe abrasiveness on SCF. It can be reasonably expected that a better dispersion state of the nanoparticles will improve the tribological

behavior of the nanocomposite slid even under a low pressure. Under pressures higher than 2 MPa, the nanoparticle agglomerates can be crushed by the counterpart into much smaller scales. Hence, compared with the wear under a low pressure, the abrasiveness on SCF exerted by the nanoparticle agglomerates can be reduced under a high pressure. In addition, the nanoparticles can reduce SCF failures by protecting SCF/matrix interfaces. This can be the main reason for the enhancement of wear resistance.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Friedrich K, Zhang Z, Schlarb AK. Effects of various fillers on the sliding wear of polymer composites. *Compos Sci Technol* 2005;65:2329-43.
- [2]. Voort J, Bahadur S. The growth and bonding of transfer film and the role of CuS and PTFE in the tribological behavior of PEEK. *Wear* 1995;181-183:212-21.
- [3]. Briscoe BJ, Yao LH, Stolarski TA. The friction and wear of poly(tetrafluoroethylene)-poly (etheretherketone) composites: An initial appraisal of the optimum composition. *Wear* 1986;108:357-74.
- [4]. Zhang MQ, Rong MZ, Yu SL, Wetzal, Friedrich K. Effect of particle surface treatment on the tribological performance of epoxy based nanocomposites. *Wear* 2002;253:1086-93.
- [5]. Voss H, Friedrich K. on the wear behaviour of short-fiber reinforced PEEK composites. *Wear* 1987;116:1-18.
- [6]. Blundell DJ, Osborn BN. The morphology of poly(aryl-ether-ether-ketone). *Polymer* 1983;25:953-8.
- [7]. Jones DP, Leach DC, Moore DC. Mechanical properties of poly(ether-ether-ketone) for engineering applications. *Polymer* 1985;26:1385-93.
- [8]. Lu ZP, Friedrich K. On sliding friction and wear of PEEK and its composites. *Wear* 1995;181-183:624-31.
- [9]. Prehn R, Hauptert F, Friedrich K. Sliding wear performance of polymer composites under abrasive and water lubricated conditions for pump applications. *Wear* 2005;259:693-6.
- [10]. Xu L, Davim JP, Cardoso R. Prediction on tribological behaviour of composite PEEK-CF30 using artificial neural networks. *J Mater Process Technol* 2007;189:374-8.
- [11]. Zhang G, Schlarb K. Correlation of the tribological behaviors with the mechanical properties of Poly-Ether-Ether-Ketones (PEEKs) with different molecular weights and their fiber filled composites. *Wear* 2009;266:337-44.
- [12]. Rong MZ, Zhang MQ, Zheng YX, Zeng HM, Walter R, Friedrich K. Structure-property relationships of irradiation grafted nano-inorganic particle filled polypropylene composites. *Polymer* 2001;42:167-83.
- [13]. Wang Q, Xu J, Shen W, Xue Q. The effect of nanometer SiC fillers on the tribological behavior of PEEK. *Wear* 1997;209:316-21.
- [14]. Zhang G, Schlarb AK, Tria S, Elkedim O. Tensile and tribological behaviors of PEEK/nano-SiO₂ composites compounded using a ball milling technique. *Compos Sci Technol* 2008;68:3073-80.
- [15]. Bahadur S, Sunkara C. Effect of transfer film structure, composition and bonding on the tribological behaviour of polyphenylene sulfide filled with nano particles of TiO₂, ZnO, CuO and SiC. *Wear* 2005;258:1411-21.

- [16]. Zhang MQ, Rong MZ, Yu SL, Wetzel B, Friedrich K. Improvement of tribological performance of epoxy by the addition of irradiation grafted nano-inorganic particles. *Macromol Mater Eng* 2002;287:111–5.
- [17]. McCook NL, Hamilton MA, Burris DL, Sawyer WG. Tribological results of PEEK nanocomposites in dry sliding against 440C in various gas environments. *Wear* 2007;262:1511-5.
- [18]. Qiao HB, Guo Q, Tian AG, Pan GL, Xu LB. A study on friction and wear characteristics of nanometer Al_2O_3 /PEEK composites under the dry sliding condition. *Tribol Int* 2007;40:105-10.
- [19]. Xue Q, Wang Q. Wear mechanisms of polyetheretherketone composites filled with various kinds of SiC. *Wear* 1997;213:54-8.
- [20]. Shi G, Zhang MQ, Rong MZ, Wetzel B, Friedrich K. Friction and wear of low nanometer Si_3N_4 filled epoxy composites. *Wear* 2003;254:784-96.
- [21]. Guo QB, Rong MZ, Jia GL, Lau KT, Zhang MQ. Sliding wear performance of nano- SiO_2 /short carbon fiber/epoxy hybrid composites. *Wear* 2009;266 658–65.
- [22]. Zhang Z, Breidt C, Chang L, Hauptert F, Friedrich K. Enhancement of the wear resistance of epoxy: short carbon fiber, graphite, PTFE and nano- SiO_2 . *Composites Part A* 2004;35:1385-92.
- [23]. Chang L, Zhang Z, Ye L, Friedrich K. Tribological properties of high temperature resistant polymer composites with fine particles. *Tribol Int* 2007;40:1170-8.
- [24]. Friedrich K, Váradi K, Goda T, Giertzsch H. Finite element analysis of a polymer composite subjected to a sliding steel asperity: Part II. Parallel and anti-parallel fiber orientations. *J Mater Sci* 2002;37:3497-507.
- [25]. Goda T, Váradi K, Wetzel B, Friedrich K. Finite element simulation of the fiber–matrix debonding in polymer composites produced by a sliding indenter: Part II–Parallel and anti-parallel fiber orientation. *J Compos Mater* 2004;38:1607-18.
- [26]. Zhang G, Liao H, Li H, Mateus C, Bordes JM, Coddet C. On dry sliding friction and wear behaviour of PEEK and PEEK/SiC-composite coatings. *Wear* 2006;260:594-600.
- [27]. Adachi K, Hutchings IM. Wear-mode mapping for the micro-scale abrasion test. *Wear* 2003;255: 23-9.
- [28]. Misra RDK, Hadal RS, Duncan SJ. Surface damage behavior during scratch deformation of mineral reinforced polymer composites. *Acta Mater* 2004;52:4363-76.